

Studies on the Flow and Sedimentation Characteristics of Sodium Bentonite Suspensions in Presence of Electrolytes and Humic Acids

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THE flow behaviour of a clay suspension is a very sensitive criterion for particle interaction. The changes in flow behaviour of clay suspensions upon (i) addition of different electrolytes, (ii) addition of the same electrolyte at different concentrations^{1,2}, (iii) addition of a polyelectrolyte, such as humic acids in (i) and (ii) above and (iv) changes of temperature in all the above cases³, provide a means for analysis of changes in particle interaction forces and modes of particle association occurring in flocculation processes.

Guha and Gupta⁴ have shown that the departure from linearity in the plot of volume concentration against relative viscosity can be taken to be the onset of structure formation. A viscometric study of the concentration dependence of dilute montmorillonite dispersions was made by Granquist⁵ both in distilled water and electrolyte containing water. The flocculating effect of anionic polyelectrolytes suspended in water, in relation to the mechanism of formation of polyanion linkage among the clay particles was studied by Diazakita and Kawaguchi⁶. The present work comprises studies on (a) the effect of the addition of different amounts of NaCl to Na-bentonite suspensions of different concentrations at room temperature (30°), (b) the stabilizing effect of humic acids addition (in different concentrations) to each of the systems mentioned above and (c) the swelling properties of clay upon the addition of humic acids.

Experimental

Preparation of clay sample and its conversion to monoionic form and measurement of C. E. C. was done according to the method reported earlier⁴. The clay samples were characterised by chemical analysis (Table 1), B. E. T. surface area and C. E. C. measurements (Table 2).

The homogenised and non-settling clay suspension at a concentration where thixotropy was absent (0.8% w/v) was mixed with different amounts of NaCl (the suspension made 0, 0.31, 0.62, 1.25, 2.5 and 5 N with respect to NaCl) and with different amounts of humic acids (1.1, 2.1, 3.5 and 4.6 mg of dry humic acids per 100 g of clay), equilibrated overnight and viscosities measured by a thermostated Ostwald viscometer at 30°. The plots of

Chemical constituent	%
Loss on ignition	12.5
SiO ₂	52.1
Al ₂ O ₃	25.8
Fe ₂ O ₃	4.7
MgO	2.1
K ₂ O	0.53
Na ₂ O	0.41

TABLE 2—THE C.E.C. AND B.E.T. SURFACE AREA OF THE SIZE SEPARATED SAMPLE

C.E.C. meq/100 g	180
Surface area m ² /g	158.5

relative viscosity versus volume concentration (of clay) at different electrolyte and humic acids concentrations are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Changes in the flow properties of Na-bentonite on the addition of NaCl of different concentrations.

○...No NaCl added
□...0.62 N NaCl added
×...2.5 N NaCl added
△...0.31 N NaCl added
●...1.25 N NaCl added
▲...5 N NaCl added

Fig. 2. Changes in the flow properties of Na-bentonite suspensions which is 5-N with respect to NaCl, on the addition of different amounts of humic acids.

○... No humic acid added
△...1.1 mg/100 g of clay, humic acid added
□...2.1 mg/100 g of clay, humic acid added
◇...3.5 mg/100 g of clay, humic acid added
×...4.6 mg/150 g of clay, humic acid added

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Fig. 3. Swelling of 0.8 Na-bentonite suspension flocculated by the addition of NaCl upon the addition of different amounts of humic acid.

For sedimentation volume studies, a 0.8% (w/v) sodium bentonite suspension was taken in a measuring cylinder and just enough 5 N NaCl solution was added until a clear supernatant liquid was observed. The suspension was left overnight and the volume of the suspension adjusted to 5 ml. Different amounts (1.1, 2.1, 3.5 and 4.8 mg) of humic acids were then added, the mixture homogenised for 4 hr and left overnight again. The final volume was then plotted against the amount of added humic acids (Fig. 3).

The humic acids used in this study were prepared by boiling powdered south Arcot lignite with 5 N NaOH, filtering and precipitating the humic acids with 2 N HCl. The precipitated humic acids were washed, dried in an air oven at 110° for 2 hr and cooled in a desiccator.

Discussion

Clay particles carry a negative charge, which is balanced by the cations adsorbed on their surfaces. Positive edge charges for montmorillonites have been reported by Van Olphen¹⁰ and Meldau *et al*⁹ but the magnitude of these edge charges is far too small compared to the surface negative charge on the clay plates. Schofield and Samson⁹ reported that the flocculation of Na-kaolinite occurs due to the electrostatic attraction between positive edges and negative faces. No conclusive evidence of a similar mechanism exists for the flocculation of montmorillonite particles. The nature and extent of charge distribution in the clay particles is dependent on isomorphous lattice substitution of divalent ions (e.g., Al³⁺ by Mg²⁺) as well as lattice distortion. The positive adsorption sites are, however, dependent on the particle size distribution of the clay material.

The addition of an electrolyte compresses the electrical double layer, presumably at the negative surface¹⁰ resulting in a stronger interparticle association with consequent change in viscosity. A departure from the linear Einstein relation would

then be expected at a lower volume concentration with increasing electrolyte concentration.

The decreasing slope in the relative viscosity versus volume concentration (of clay) curves upon increasing electrolyte concentration (Fig. 1) supports this mechanism.

A polyelectrolyte (such as humic acids) has a polar group attached to a non-polar macromolecular tail. This will effectively screen the double layer from compression on the addition of an electrolyte. Thus, the addition of a polyelectrolyte is expected to annul or suppress the effect of electrolyte addition. An increase in floc volume on the addition of a polyelectrolyte is also expected.

The increasing slope in the relative viscosity vs volume concentration (of clay) (Fig. 2) and increasing sedimentation volume (upto a limiting value) (Fig. 3) upon the addition of increasing amounts of humic acids supports this contention.

Conclusion: From a study of the flow properties of Na-bentonite suspensions in the presence of NaCl solutions of different concentrations and upon the addition of different amounts of humic acids, it was found that (a) electrolyte addition favours flocculation and reduction in viscosity of the suspensions and (b) humic acids (which are essentially polyelectrolytes) annul or suppress the effect of electrolyte addition and tend to increase the viscosity and floc volume of the clay suspensions.

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2-Aryl amino-4-[4'-(benzene sulphonamido)-phenyl]-thiazoles

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VARIOUS 2-substituted amino-4-[4'(benzene sulphonamido)-phenyl]-thiazoles have been synthesized to study their anti bacterial activity.

The starting materials, 4-(4'-aminophenyl)-2-aryl amino)-thiazoles, were synthesized by condensing *p*-acetamido- ω -chloroacetophenone with substituted phenyl thioureas in alcohol. The thioureas used were phenyl, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chlorophenyl, *o*-methoxyphenyl, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-methylphenyl, *o*-nitrophenyl and (2'-pyridyl)-thioureas. 4-(4'-Acetamidophenyl)-2-(substituted amino)-thiazoles were hydrolysed to 4-(4'-aminophenyl)-2-(substituted amino)-thiazoles (I) which on reacting with *p*-substituted phenyl sulphonyl chloride yielded compounds of the type (II). It should be noted here that 4-(4'-acetamido-phenyl)-2-(substituted

amino)-thiazoles did not give any reaction product with *p*-substituted phenyl sulphonyl chloride.

Hence, the primary amino group condenses with sulphonyl chloride group in the formation of the compounds (II). The ir spectra confirmed the presence of O=S=O grouping in these compounds from their strong absorption at $\sim 1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (asymmetric stretch) and $\sim 1125\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (symmetric stretch). The thiazole nucleus showed absorption bands at 1570-1530, 1438-1380 and 1390-1330 cm^{-1} . The two bands in the region 3500-3260 and 3220-3180 cm^{-1} are due to $-\text{SO}_2-\text{NH}$ and $-\text{NH}-$ stretchings. The $-\text{NH}-$ bending absorption was observed at 1610-1580 cm^{-1} .

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-137 spectrophotometer in KBr phase.

Synthesis of 4-(4'-aminophenyl)-2-(substituted amino)-thiazoles (I): A mixture of *p*-acetamido- ω -chloro-acetophenone (0.1 mole), substituted phenyl

TABLE-1

Substituents R	4-(4'-aminophenyl)-2(substituted amino)-thiazole (I)		4-[4'-(<i>p</i> -substituted benzene sulphonamido)-phenyl]-2(substituted amino)-thiazoles (II)		Substituent R'			NH ₂				
					-CH ₃							
	m.p. °C	N% Found (Calcd.)	S% Found (Calcd.)	m.p. °C	N% Found (Calcd.)	S% Found (Calcd.)	m.p. °C	N% Found (Calcd.)	S% Found (Calcd.)	m.p. °C	N% Found (Calcd.)	S% Found (Calcd.)
Phenyl	121	15.52 (15.72)	11.54 (11.98)	142	10.12 (9.97)	15.30 (15.20)	152	11.97 (12.07)	14.48 (14.16)	162	13.14 (13.24)	15.60 (15.16)
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	210	13.84 (13.95)	10.52 (10.63)	196	9.14 (9.28)	14.32 (14.06)	192	11.34 (11.28)	12.62 (12.35)	196	12.92 (12.24)	13.92 (14.08)
<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	104	13.81 (13.95)	10.61 (10.63)	179	9.40 (9.29)	14.40 (14.06)	124	11.27 (11.28)	12.59 (12.85)	191	12.28 (12.24)	14.37 (14.09)
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	212	13.75 (13.95)	10.65 (10.63)	192	9.37 (9.28)	14.29 (14.06)	183	11.37 (11.28)	12.59 (12.85)	189	12.31 (12.24)	14.29 (14.09)
<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	203	14.25 (14.14)	10.53 (10.77)	187	9.50 (9.27)	14.00 (14.19)						
<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	142	14.65 (14.95)	10.32 (11.39)	138	9.71 (9.65)	14.92 (14.71)	192	11.74 (11.68)	13.22 (13.38)	180	12.93 (12.81)	14.62 (14.67)
<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	157	15.01 (14.95)	11.49 (11.39)	217	9.73 (9.65)	14.95 (14.71)	146	11.57 (11.68)	13.29 (13.38)	226	12.87 (12.81)	14.06 (14.67)
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	146	17.93 (18.12)	10.32 (10.25)	149	11.85 (12.02)	14.71 (13.78)	145	13.81 (13.75)	12.35 (12.75)	298	15.10 (14.95)	13.62 (13.73)
(2'-Pyridyl)-	240	20.74 (20.89)	11.72 (11.94)				179	14.94 (15.09)	14.98 (15.18)	184	16.64 (16.55)	15.29 (15.18)